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METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D4.4

METICOS System Architecture

(first version)

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Terms and abbreviations

ADME	Advance Data Mining Engine
API	Application Programming Interface
AThAM	Automated Threshold Assessment Module
BCP	Border Control Point
BDA	Big Data Analytics
CDME	Common Data Management Engine
CS	Cross Sectorial
DTVA	Data, Text & Visual Analytics
EC	European Commission
ETAP	Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction
HDP	Hierarchical Dirichlet Process
LSA	Latent Semantic Analysis
ML	Machine Learning
NER	Named Entity Recognizer
NLP	Natural Language Processing
POS	Part of Speech
RP	Random Projections
SCFM	Socio-Cultural Framework Module
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
VIS	Visa Information System
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The deliverable *D4.4 METICOS System Architecture (first version)* describes the results of the task *T4.3 Technology Exploration & Reference Architecture Design* that is scheduled in M3-M12, M19-M22, M29-M32. It presents the first version of the METICOS system architecture. It gives details about the “4+1” methodology used to create the architecture. It presents details about the components that collaborate in the METICOS system. It describes the architecture using logical view, process view, development view, deployment view + scenario.

This deliverable will be followed by the D4.7 that will present the final version of the METICOS architecture.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

The deliverable D4.4 presents the first version of the reference architecture of the METICOS platform. The architecture presented here is based on the project objectives and current understanding of the user needs. It relies on the requirement analysis done in task T4.1 and presented in deliverable D4.1. It also relies on discussions with end user partners in the context of other work packages (WP5, WP6, WP7).

It is expected that the architecture will evolve as the requirements are refined and platform components are developed. The updated architecture will be presented in deliverable D4.7, due M29.

1.2 Document structure

Section 2 of this document contains the requirements gathered in deliverable D4.1, mapped on components, with the associated MoSCoW priority [1]. Section 3 explores other relevant European projects and how they contributed to the METICOS architecture and design. Section 3 also details the METICOS components and presents an analysis for the technological choices made. Section 4 describes the METICOS architecture through the five views prescribed by the “4+1” View Model of Software Architecture methodology [2]. Section 5 contains the conclusions and future work.

1.3 Methodology

For the development of the architecture of the METICOS platform we used as reference ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011 *Systems and software engineering - Architecture description* [3]. It describes a set of principles and concepts that are the foundation of producing an architectural description that captures the relevant information to the stakeholders.

Although ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011 contains requirements for architecture descriptions, architecture frameworks and architecture description languages and architecture viewpoints, for this deliverable we are interested in the requirements for the architecture descriptions, organized in the following categories:

- architecture description and overview – describe the system of interest, versioning information about the document containing the architecture description
- system stakeholders and their concerns – list the stakeholders and their main concerns regarding the system.
- viewpoints and views – describe the system from the point of view of different stakeholders. The concerns of stakeholders should be addressed.
- relations – describe the relations between the architecture description elements
- rationale – document the reason for viewpoints used and important decisions being made

We used the “4+1” View Model of Software Architecture as an architectural framework to produce the architectural description. In the context of ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011 an architectural framework is a verified approach to the creation, analysis and interpretation of architecture descriptions.

The “4+1” View Model of Software Architecture was published by Philippe Kruchten in 1995 [2]. This paper proposes the use of multiple views to describe the architecture of a system. Each view describes the system considering the concerns of a specific group of stakeholders. The process proposed by this paper is iterative. The views are validated against the scenarios and then updated based on the new information obtained.

The “4+1” View Model of Software Architecture, in the initial form, uses 4 views and some relevant scenarios, that become another view. This is represented in Figure 1.

A short presentation of the views follows:

- Logical view (functional view) – it describes the functional requirements of the system, the components of the system and their relationships, components responsibilities and interfaces.
- Process view – this view is focused on the dynamic aspect of the system, on the collaborations and interactions between the system’s components. This view is also used to describe non-functional requirements like performance, availability, scalability.
- Physical view (deployment view) – it maps the elements from the architecture to equipment/location.
- Development view – it contains details about the software components used in the developing the system. It gives details like programming languages, libraries, toolsets.
- Scenarios – the scenarios are used to demonstrate that the elements in the other views collaborate effectively. This process allows also to discover missing architectural elements. The scenarios are useful later for validation and documentation of the system.

Figure 1: The “4+1” view model

(source: [2] Philippe Kruchten, Architectural Blueprints)

The views will be presented in chapter 4 METICOS System Architecture.

2 System requirements and specifications

2.1 Functional requirements

2.1.1 Data Integration Module / Common Data Management Engine (CDME)

The “Data Integration Module / Common Data Management Engine (CDME)” component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	MoSCoW Priority
Storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way	METICOS Common Data Management Engine (CDME) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way. All the exchanged information will be translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all METICOS components use them. It will contain information about the METICOS Ecosystem static information such as building architectural map, actors, procedures, and equipment related to the project, installed sensors that will be used, etc. Furthermore, it will include the dynamic aspects related to the METICOS Ecosystem, including events and context information (e.g. location, time, etc.), alerts, measurements, events related to re-adaptation and training activities and social platform, etc.	Must have

2.1.2 Advance Data Mining Engine for Unstructured data

The Advanced Data Mining Engine for Unstructured data has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Data preprocessing (removal of stop words, POS tagging, feature extraction)	Since we are referring to unstructured data, and more specifically text, the anonymised data will proceed to the machine learning Natural Language Processing pipeline, which includes the following steps: preprocessing (removal of stop words, noise removal, POS tagging, feature	Must have

	extraction)	
Data analysis using various ML algorithms and techniques	Data analysis using various ML algorithms and techniques (LDA, TDIDF vectorization and more).	Must have
Data collection and data flow requirement	<p>To retrieve this information, a Twitter data collector application downloads any related tweets periodically and provides them as input to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data module. The data we retrieve are the date and time the tweet has been posted, the tweet’s text, the tweet ID, number of retweets and likes, and the tweet’s location. All other information is discarded. After retrieving the above information, the tweet ID is then anonymized. Some techniques could include Generalization, Data substitution and Data Shuffling. The ADME for Unstructured Data module uses the information provided by the Twitter data collector application as input, aiming to process the tweet’s text and derive the overall sentiment of the tweets, their geographic distribution and the context of discussion.</p> <p>Tweets are stored on a database for a limited time period, and as soon as they are processed, they are deleted. The only information stored is the aggregated results from the analysis performed above (sentiment, context of discussion, geographic distribution). The results obtained from the analysis are presented to the end-users through an interactive Dashboard (DTVA module).</p>	Must have
Extract data from social media	The engine will be capable of extracting data from social media (twitter, reviews, blogs) in a real-time automated way and storing it with the aim of further processing the data.	Must have

<p>Detect sentiment and context from data</p>	<p>The engine will include the functionality of sentiment detection and context detection (most important words, clustering) of social media data (twitter, reviews, blogs) in order to capture the general acceptance and social acceptance of SBC technologies. The user will be able to see most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that people are talking about regarding smart border control technologies and the BCP, subjectivity classification, hashtags and keyword analysis etc.</p>	<p>Must have</p>
<p>Generate correlations of data from multiple sources</p>	<p>The engine will be able to calculate the correlations between the unstructured data. This data includes social media data, real-time data from pilot execution (questionnaires, tweets etc), free text from the questionnaires from WP6, potentially outputs from simulation engine from WP7 , and others. The user will be able to see the correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, time series representation of the data in dynamic scale, ranking of categorical variables, outlier/anomaly detection etc. This visualisation is part of task T9.3 (component DTVA).</p>	<p>Should have</p>

2.1.3 Advance Data Mining Engine for Structured Data

The Advanced Data Mining Engine for Structured data has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
<p>Generate correlations of structured data from multiple sources</p>	<p>The engine will be able to calculate the correlations between the data available and accessible. The user will be able to see the correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, time series representation of the data in dynamic scale, ranking of categorical variables, outlier/anomaly detection etc. This visualisation is part of task T9.3 Thus, the user will be able to deduct knowledge on how some characteristics such as demographics, waiting time, overall time to pass the borders, impact the acceptance of SBC technologies.</p>	<p>Should have</p>

Data pre-processing	Data pre-processing (cleaning, outlier detection, missing data treatment).	Must have
Data analysis	Data analysis using various ML algorithms and techniques (NB, Logistic Regression, Neural Networks, Ensemble methods and others). Moreover, the impact of demographics/profile data of travellers and border guards, the waiting time, time to cross the border, and other influencing factors, will be analysed against acceptance.	Must have
Descriptive analytics for indicators of acceptance and other parameters	Descriptive analytics for indicators of acceptance (e.g. timeseries representation, changes over time and among different geolocations, number of users etc). Descriptive analytics for parameters influencing acceptance such as time to cross the border, queue length... (e.g. timeseries representation, changes over time etc).	Must have

2.1.4 Embedded Technology Acceptance Algorithms

The “Embedded Technology Acceptance Algorithms” component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Single predictions based on structural equations	The stateless model takes data as input parameters for making single predictions based on structural equations.	Must have
Quantification of social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution	The ETAP module is grounded on one or more probabilistic technology acceptance models (TAMs) which are developed during the project. The probabilistic modelling will be based on existing literature (technology acceptance, expectancy and quality of experience research, existing acceptance models) as well as datasets generated during the project by means of user studies and surveys. The model itself consists of several components that reflect the most relevant key aspects (perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, etc.) of acceptance of smart border control technologies.	Must have

User Interface (End User)	The interface displays numerical values (e.g. percent) representing acceptance related factors (e.g., intention to use, easiness of usages, trust, etc) based on the calculations of the ETAP module. Dashboard widgets are used to display these values, e.g., gauge, bullet graphs, bar charts, etc.).	Must have
User Interface (Admin User)	This is an extension to the interface for end users (see line above). An admin user is able to change several parameters of the underlying ETAP module to evaluate how acceptance is affected if e.g. demographic aspects of travelers are changed.	Should have

2.1.5 Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit

The Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Visualise correlations of data from multiple sources	The user will have a view of the visual output produced in other modules, namely ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data and CS-BDA. Some examples include social media context analysis (most important words, clustering), time series of waiting time, acceptance score. More information can be found in each respective component. Moreover, the user will be able to see a live feed of twitter streams for the BCP of their interest.	Must have
Produce further analysis of existing and new data	The user can explore the data and their correlations in more detail, by for example, changing some parameters, or selecting part of it and viewing some of its characteristics in more detail. Furthermore, the user will be able to import new datasets, create new correlations between new and/or existing data, and perform further in-depth analysis.	Could have
Visualisation of indicators, report on analysis, etc.	The data will be displayed to the end users of METICOS. This component will not further process the data, it will serve as a visualisation module.	Must have

2.1.6 Cross-sectorial (big) data analysis mechanisms

The Cross-sectorial Big Data Analysis mechanisms component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
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Aggregate multi-modal data from other METICOS components	Building upon the results of each dataset (incl. data sources providing structured & unstructured data, output from other METICOS components), the user can view the overall acceptance score for all BCPs and understand better the acceptance based on different criteria.	Must have
Predict acceptance	The user will be able to predict the acceptance of the SBC technologies of a "new" BCP (a BCP for which no analysis has been conducted) based on available data from other BCPs. <i>(cross-sector analysis of acceptance).</i>	Could have
Data analyses	Data analysis using various ML algorithms and techniques (NB, Logistic Regression, Neural Networks, Ensemble methods and others).	Must have
Descriptive analytics for indicators of acceptance	Descriptive analytics for indicators of acceptance.	Must have
Patterns definitions	Patterns will be discovered in the combination of data from various sources, different locations and different formats.	Must have
Produce the overall acceptance score for all BCPs	This component, using the output of the components ADME for unstructured data, ADME from structured data and ETAP, will produce the overall acceptance score for all BCP's and help the user understand better the criteria which influence the acceptance of SBCT.	Must have

2.1.7 Automated tools for assessing the thresholds for the use and adopting of technology where non-EU citizens react

The “Automated tools for assessing the thresholds for the use and adopting of technology where non-EU citizens react” component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Define main input parameters	As related to the acceptance rate for diverse BCP technologies, this module should help us define the main parameters needed in the process. We will consider different sources of information when it comes to the given technology and other context-related data	Should have

Define the input-output relation	The module should be able to make use of the advanced tools and methods incorporated to decide properly the best-fit model for providing outcomes of high relevance to the Social sensing toolkit, in terms of the BCP technologies involved	Should have
Define the specific threshold for each BCP technology	Once the main input parameters and the model is properly defined, the module should be able to correctly tune the threshold level for a given BCP technology, based also on local context. The whole process will be affected from continuous updates based on feedback from existing modules within the Social sensing toolkit and others.	Must have

2.1.8 Simulation tools for different behavioural patterns - METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit

The “METICOS Social SensingToolkit” component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Analyzing the impact of the total crossing time	Analyzing the impact of the total crossing time on SBC technology acceptance.	Must have
Treatment of missing data of the travellers	Identification and inputation of missing data of the travellers.	Should have
Analyzing the impact of demographics/profile data of the travellers	Analyzing the impact of demographics/profile data of the travellers over technology acceptance.	Should have
Descriptive statistics on demographics	Descriptive statistics on demographics and comparisons of technology acceptance level by demographics.	Should have
Defining rules for technology acceptance	Defining rules for technology acceptance for SBC technologies.	Must have
Treatment of missing data of the border staff members	Identification and inputation of missing data of the travellers.	Should have
Analyzing the impact of demographics/profile data of the border staff members	Analyzing the impact of demographics/profile data of the border staff members over technology acceptance.	Should have
Descriptive statistics on border staffs	Descriptive statistics on demographics and comparisons of technology acceptance level by border staffs.	Should have

Defining rules for technology acceptance	Defining rules for technology acceptance for SBC technologies.	Should have
Analyzing the impact of demographics/profile data of the traveller who pressed the smiley face	Analyzing the impact of demographics/profile data of the traveller who pressed the smiley face over the output of the smiley face.	Should have
Extraction of the responses provided by the end-users	Extraction of the responses provided by the end-users from structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes.	Should have
Manually extract the perceptions from the answers to the questions	Manually extract the perceptions from the answers to the questions.	Should have
Sentiment analysis on the provided answers	Performing sentiment analysis on the provided answers will lead to understanding emotions and opinions for SBC technologies.	Should have
Text pre-processing techniques in order to clean the text	Text pre-processing techniques in order to clean the text.	Should have
Tweets analysis regarding the acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies	Extract topics and opinions as well as sentiments from the tweets in order to understand if the traveller has accepted the SBC technology while its travel or not.	Should have
Define input level and values	Here we will be able to define a list of parameters as appropriate inputs to the tool, along with respective values according to some pre-defined boundaries and other attributes.	Should have
Define output level and values	Here we will be able to define a list of parameters as appropriate inputs to the tool, such as the technology acceptance decision, success rates etc.	Should have
Define the mapping level	Define a proper relation between the input and output parameters - the equation - that will be able to explain and predict the final result.	Should have

2.1.9 Socio-cultural framework

The “Socio-cultural framework” component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Define input parameters	After collecting relevant information about state-of-the-art for the relevant work in the previous tasks, we will be able to define the	Must have

	final list of parameters as appropriate inputs to the SCFM, such as age, gender, social status, education, lifestyle etc. along with appropriate values as related to the objectives set for this task.	
Define output parameters	Here we will also make use of completed work/deliverables to be able to define a final list of parameters as appropriate outputs to the module, that will be continuously revised in terms of their impact on the final decision making process.	Must have
Map input and output parameters	The ongoing tasks will help us define the appropriate model explaining the relationship between the input and output parameters - the main equation - that should provide optimal solution to the task given. This will also be part of a continuous process aiming for the best solutions.	Must have

2.1.10 Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform

The scope of the project was changed so the METICOS system will not connect to custom identification systems or BCP risk assessment platforms. Further to this METICOS platform will not be connected with any VIS or SIS or any other border information system for security reasons. This component will be modified or will be no longer implemented in v2.

2.1.11 Smart Front-End Infrastructure

The “Smart Front-End Infrastructure” component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Visualisation of data fusion	Implementation of Front End platform for visualisation of data fusion intended for border authorities.	Must have

2.1.12 Interfaces with customs identification systems

The scope of the project was changed so the METICOS system will not connect to custom identification systems or BCP risk assessment platforms. Further to this METICOS platform will not be connected with any VIS or ISIS or any other border information system for security reasons. This component will be modified or will be no longer implemented in v2.

2.1.13 Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems

The scope of the project was changed so the METICOS system will not connect to custom identification systems or BCP risk assessment platforms. Further to this METICOS platform will not be connected with any VIS or SIS or any other border information system for security reasons. This component will be modified or will be no longer implemented in v2.

2.1.14 METICOS Middleware

The “METICOS Middleware” component has the following functional requirements:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Return Passenger Information upon request	METICOS middleware will be a software system that will facilitate data communication between identification equipment, such as sensors, risk management methods and border authorities and law enforcement information systems.	Must have
Event Filtering	Filtering of information coming in from sensors for the purpose of facilitating the storage and handling of heterogeneous data.	Should have
Information Aggregation, Storage, mining	Aggregation of data for purposes of statistical analysis and for discovery of patterns within the data set.	Must have
Authentication	Security layer for authentication of users accessing the system.	Must have
Encryption	Encryption and privacy for transmission of sensitive, personal data and sensors.	Must have
Travellers data anonymization	Data anonymization of the demographics and profile data of the travellers.	Should have
Border staff members data anonymization	Anonymization of the demographics and profile data of the border staff members.	Should have
Data anonymization	Data anonymization/pseudoanonymization to ensure the protection of personal data.	Should have

2.2 Nonfunctional requirements

The non functional requirements identified so far are presented in the following table:

Requirement	Description	Priority
Future Proofing	The METICOS System shall be able to be improved with the future addition of new data and data sources.	Should have
User Friendliness	The METICOS System shall present data in a comprehensive, user-friendly and intuitive manner for users.	Must have
Security	The METICOS System shall implement secure data transmission between its components and between itself and other systems (such as Border Authorities' Systems, etc.). A security	Must have

	layer for authentication, encryption and privacy for transmission of sensitive data (including personal data) shall be implemented.	
Privacy	The METICOS System shall be implemented in line with privacy legal regulations and ethical standards at EU and relevant national levels.	Must have

3 Technology exploration

3.1 State of the Art Analysis of Relevant Research Projects

3.1.1 Relevant European Projects

There are an important number of projects that are researching and innovating in the smart borders field. To understand the state of the art in the domain we selected and studied a sample of them. The most relevant projects we selected are described below:

- **TRESPASS (robust Risk basEd Screening and alert System for PASSengers and luggage)**
This project has as a scope the development of risk based security checks, replacing the current rule based security check approach. It leverages the smart border technologies in order to collect data and build risk models that are used to decide the level of detail of security checks at border control points. This approach will lead to increased traffic flow at BPC because only the passengers with high risk are subject to time consuming security checks. The project ensures legal and ethical compliance by applying an ethics and data protection by design approach.
- **iBorderCtrl (Intelligent Portable Border Control System)**
This project aims at increasing the speed of border control for 3rd country nationals that are crossing the land borders of EU member states. This is realised by using software and hardware technologies like portable readers and scanners (biometric module for fingerprints and palm vein detection, facial recognition, document scanners), subsystems for automatic control (hidden human detection tool, risk-based assessment tool, automatic deception detection system), wireless networking for mobile controls, secure backend storage and processing.
- **PERSONA (Privacy, Ethical, Regulatory and SOcial “No-gate crossing point solution” Acceptance)**
This project has the goal to provide the guidelines needed by the border authorities to assess and choose no-gated border crossing solutions that inspire the general public confidence in their security, safety, legality and ethical soundness. The project analyses state-of-the-art contactless crossing point technologies, their risks and benefits considering their effectiveness, human behaviour, societal and privacy issues, data protection and potential for discrimination.
- **SMILE (SMart mobilLity at the European land borders)**
The SMILE project explores the improvements at land border control points through the use of smart mobile devices in biometric control. This allows the reduction of resources needed at border control point by using low-cost technological solutions that implement secure and trusted authentication. The project uses a private cloud infrastructure that contains various services like biometric verification services, risk assessment/alerts management, statistics and reporting.
- **Smart Trust: Secure Mobile ID for Trusted Smart Borders**
This project produces a new platform for Mobile ID that increases the reliability and trust level of identity verification at European borders. The platform ensures the travellers privacy by implementing privacy by design principles. Smart Trust is based on a highly configurable, modular and open architecture platform.

By analyzing these projects, we extracted some important principles that will be given attention in METICOS:

- *Ethics*
Ethics is given important attention in the project. WP1 and its deliverables are dedicated to ethics requirements. WP3 package will develop an ethics handbook for doing research, tests

and demonstration. It will also coordinate with other work packages in order to conduct privacy, ethical, social and data protection impact assessment of METICOS.

- *Privacy*

The development of METICOS architecture and components is centered around principles and best practices derived from the Privacy by Design concept [3]. One principle is to be proactive and prevent risk incidents instead of being reactive and offer remedies. On this regard, the access to METICOS platform will be restricted to authorized users, only needed ports will be open in the firewall, the latest version of software components will be used in order to prevent the exploitation of known vulnerabilities. Other principles are to have privacy mechanisms active by default and embedded into the design and architecture of the system. Also, an important principle is end-to-end security meaning that the data is securely captured, stored and eventually destroyed when it's no longer needed. For this, encrypted communication will be implemented with the end users and between servers, sensitive data will be encrypted on the storage. Also, anonymization mechanisms will be used to protect personal or sensitive data.

- *Platform modularity*

By implementing a modular platform, the functionalities of the METICOS system are delegated to specific modules. The modules can evolve and can be tested independently. This leads to a more agile approach in developing the system. The communication between modules is based on REST services and standard protocols.

- *Private cloud*

The METICOS platform will be running on a software infrastructure based on Docker and Kubernetes. This approach provides flexibility about deployment scenarios: the platform can be deployed on a server or multiple servers running inside a private datacenter or it can be deployed on a public cloud. This approach also ensures the scalability of the system, both vertically (by adding more CPU cores, RAM or storage) or horizontally (by using more servers in Kubernetes cluster).

3.1.2 Technology exploration component Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP)

3.1.2.1 Technologies used

The ETAP Module is based on Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The concept has been adapted and extended during the last decades (TAM2, TAM3, UTAUT, etc) and has been applied in various application concepts. Acceptance modelling is used to accompany product and service development processes to guarantee user friendly outputs. Every acceptance model needs to be designed for a specific use case. Thus, at the beginning of the project requirements and scenario-specific information is collected to develop an acceptance model. During the execution of the related tasks, empirical data based on surveys is added to the model to quantify acceptance.

The ETAP module receives a tuple of input information (border control technology in focus, user description) describing a single case (user-technology interaction). Module will then predict likely acceptance/non-acceptance of given border control technology solution by defined target users or user groups, grounded on probabilistic technology acceptance models (TAMs). To this end, it will process feature data describing relevant influence factors and generate a score vector describing likelihood of acceptance as well as other related metrics required by the Data Integration Module and Big Data engine.

Figure 2 ETAP module technology overview

To develop the TAM model, we rely on Python and R programming language. Development environment consists of docker containers build from existing public docker images:

- **Jupyter Datascience notebook image:**
 - Python 3.x, conda, mamba, ipython
 - Notebook, Jupyterhub and Jupyterlab
 - Tex Live, Git, Vim, Nano, Scipy, pandas, scikit
 - R interpreter, IRKernel
 - Tidyverse and various R libraries
- **Rocker RStudio images:**
 - Rstudio server
 - Tidyverse, verse and ggplot libraries

For the production system, ETAP module will be implemented as Python/R module, which will communicate with external modules via REST API. Configuration is foreseen on for Admin users and therefore there is a need for core system which would allow these actions:

- model import/export
- manual model update
- evt. activate/deactivate certain parts of the model (TBD)
- activate/deactivate online model retraining
- monitor/roll back online mode retraining

To achieve this, the ETAP will be delivered as docker image, which consist of different parts allowing communication with external modules:

- NodeJS core server (NodeJS v16) running Koa.js JavaScript framework to build API
- NginX reverse proxy to offer internal module communication with different parts of the ETAP module
- Python 3.x
- R interpreter
- Docker

3.1.2.2 *Brief description of the main technological alternatives*

As an alternative to technologies mentioned in Chapter 3.1.2.1 might be used any scripting/programming language suitable to be used for data analysis. Most common alternatives for performing data analysis are these (but not limited to):

- MATLAB
- Scala
- Julia
- SAS

For building standalone module which can be embedded to METICOS platform, any of the following technologies might be used:

- Python
- C++/C#
- PHP
- Ruby
- Any JavaScript framework for server use
- Kubernetes

3.1.2.3 *Advantages over alternatives*

Decision to use technologies mentioned in the Chapter 3.1.2.1 has been made on facts, that these are currently the most popular and widely adopted technologies for this kind of development environments. All the technologies used are open sourced and commonly used in other research projects. Due to the popularity and wide adoption, the problem of maintenance and updates is greatly minimized. Python is also being used by other METICOS modules, which adds to better consistency and stability of the whole system. We avoid using proprietary frameworks (such as C# and .NET) as these are often connected with increased running and maintenance costs, which are not optimal for projects like METICOS.

3.1.3 **Technology exploration component Social Sensing Toolkit**

3.1.3.1 *Technologies used*

The METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit is the module which mainly extracts perceptions of the travelers and border staff using the techniques explained below. The online and physical data sources are used as inputs to this module as well as the profiles and rules received from the Socio Cultural Framework Module (SCFM). Once the perceptions are extracted, these perceptions are paired with profiles coming from the SCFM. That is, we generate a pool of (profile, perception) pairs which will be used for training and validating the Agent based Simulations Module along with the rules already obtained in the SCFM. The high-level architecture of the METICOS Social Toolkit is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3 General Architecture for METICOS Social Toolkit

The detailed explanation of the general architecture given in Figure 2 is provided in D6.2.

Technologies for Social Sensing The module has major input from the online social media and web data. The selected technology for this stage is “Python”; one of the most popular and open-source programming language. Specifically, we are planning to use some of the major techniques from literature related to natural language processing (NLP), machine learning and deep learning since we will be working with unstructured text data from online social media and web platforms. Figure 4 shows some of the major steps involved in social sensing; implementing these steps will ultimately lead us to extract user’s perceptions for border control technologies. These perceptions will be used in the simulation engine in order to enhance learning of the social toolkit to predict technology acceptance for border control technologies. The detailed list of planned technologies is given below:

- i) Data collection from Twitter: We are planning to implement “Twitter API v2” using python programming language in order to collect data from twitter.
- ii) Data collection from Web: We are planning to implement web crawlers using “Beautiful Soap API” to crawl relevant data from blogs, news websites, etc.
- iii) Handling unstructured text data: Luckily, python has an excellent pool of several libraries available in order to work with text data. These libraries provide easy functions to preprocess the text data. Some of the libraries in our plan includes NLTK, Spacy, Gensim, Matplotlib, Plotly, pandas, numpy, etc.
- iv) Extracting user’s perceptions: We are planning to use some of the recent libraries which will help us to extract user’s perceptions from the text data. The list is from recent machine as well as deep learning libraries in python consisting of tensorflow, keras, transformers, hugging face, VADER, TextBlob, etc. These libraries will help us to implement some of the major components involved below:
 - a. Intent Classification
 - b. Subjectivity Classification
 - c. Sentiment Classification
 - d. Aspect Classification
 - e. Keyword / Keyphrase Extraction
- v) The aggregations of the extracted perceptions will be used as data and rules in the social toolkit.

Figure 4 Methodology for performing social sensing

Technologies for Agent Based Modelling and Simulation

We are planning to use “AnyLogic”; a multimethod modelling and simulation tool as a proposed technology for the development of agent-based modelling and simulation stage in the METICOS Social Toolkit. The details of the selected technology tool is already defined in the “**D6.1 - Survey and State of the Art about possible social sources**”. It is a unique tool that combines System Dynamics, Discrete Event, and Agent-Based modelling methods into a one model development environment, allowing the AnyLogic software to provide a great deal of flexibility with its built-in Java capabilities, as all the simulation's complex agent behaviour can be modelled with Java coding.

We already started working with some initial simulations to further explore the “AnyLogic” technology tool. The additional details regarding the initial simulations is given in section “**4.4 - Requirements of the agent-based simulation tool**” of **D6.1**.

3.1.3.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

Technology Alternatives for Social Sensing

There are other programming languages available as well for performing same kind of steps which we are implementing using python technology tool. Some of the other tools are:

- R Programming Language
- Java Programming Language
- GATE Text Analytics Tool
- PHP Programming Language
- CoreNLP

Technology Alternatives for Agent Based Modelling and Simulation

There are many technology alternatives for designing agent-based modelling and simulations. Some of these are CloudSim, Eve, EcoLab, CybelPro. The details regarding these alternatives are already explained in the “**D6.1**” under section “**3.3.4 - Tools for designing agent-based simulation**”.

3.1.3.3 Advantages over alternatives

The major advantages of the AnyLogic tool over other alternatives are:

- 1) It is a general-purpose tool for designing agent-based modelling and simulations
- 2) The modelling strength is very large in terms of designing complex scenarios
- 3) The tool itself is not very complex to work with
- 4) It supports integration of external databases for input and output data
- 5) It supports the integration of other programming languages like python, R, etc.

The information is taken from “**Table 3 - CloudSim, Eve, EcoLab, Cybelpro & AnyLogic ABMS tools**” in **D6.1**.

The major advantages of the Python programming language over other alternatives are:

- 1) It is a high-level language containing English-like syntax; which is easy to read, write and understand.
- 2) It involves writing less amount of the code as compared to other languages while performing any simple task

- 3) It is free and open source
- 4) It has vast amount of libraries over 200,000, available to accomplish many of the complex tasks in general programming, machine learning, text analysis, deep learning, etc.
- 5) It has a wide support of contributors from all over the world for developing new libraries and making them open source.

The information is taken from “**Table 3 - CloudSim, Eve, EcoLab, Cybelpro & AnyLogic ABMS tools**” in **D6.1**.

3.1.4 Technology exploration component Socio-cultural framework

3.1.4.1 Technologies used

The socio-cultural framework module (SCFM) will allow the METICOS platform to assess the main reasons behind possible misunderstandings that may occur when individuals with different sociocultural backgrounds will try to pass through new BCP technologies. This module will provide inputs to the METICOS Social Toolkit. That is, this component is related to the findings of main factors and reasons for how technology acceptance of people from various social and cultural backgrounds vary depending on the connected parameters such as age, cultural background, educational backgrounds etc. This module interfaces the online and physical data sources and identifies patterns (rules) in the data and extract profiles and demographics of persons using borders (travelers) and persons working at the borders (border staff). The rules may be both hand crafted from the data available and also can be automatically extracted from data using machine and deep learning techniques. We estimate rules to be in the form of “person profile → a type of perception”. An example synthetic rule would be “a person over age of 80 perceives the biometrics based verification technology difficult to use”. The rules and the profiles extracted from the data sources are provided as input to the Social Sensing Toolkit Module.

We are planning to use the “Python” programming language for this technology component. Specifically, we will be using some of the libraries like Scikit-learn, mlxtend, etc to create correlation tables, graphs and matrices between a traveller’s and border staff’s socio-cultural parameters and their experience with the border control technology. The correlations will help us to understand the influence of such parameters for the acceptance of a specific border control technology.

3.1.4.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

As explained earlier, SCFM will extract profiles of the travellers and border staff whereas the social sensing toolkit will extract perceptions of the target groups. There is a correlation between the tools to be used for perception and profile extraction. For that reason, as well as the technology, technology alternatives for profile extractions are the same with alternatives defined in section 3.1.3.

3.1.4.3 Advantages over alternatives

Since the technologies are the same both for profile and perception extraction, the advantages are also the same. Please refer to section 3.1.3 for advantages.

3.1.5 Technology exploration component Automated tools for assessing threshold

3.1.5.1 Technologies used

The Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) will define a specific threshold for each BCP technology when dealing with non-EU travelers. It will be an external component supporting the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit with continuous feeds from real-time data. The module will use information collected from different sources, mostly related to the different technologies and devices in use, such as the overall complexity of the device/technology used, the level of interaction

with different users, response time, the level of flexibility, level of necessary support from border authorities etc. Similar with the SCFM, AThAM will aim to use context-based data to adjust the threshold accordingly.

Initial values of thresholds will be obtained from local authorities, based on their experience and knowledge from existing BCP technologies used. These values will be matched with the existing BCP technologies to define a model that will explain the threshold level based on the parameters above and others introduced further.

Because this module will get initial data from local authorities related to border technologies and thresholds for their acceptance level under certain conditions. We are planning to use “Python” as a technology tool for this component. Specifically, we will be planning to design different classification or regression-based models using machine as well as deep learning libraries like scikit-learn, keras, etc. Once, these models are trained on data from local authorities, they can be used for predicting automated threshold for the border technologies based on provided input.

3.1.5.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

Same as technology alternatives defined in section 3.1.3.

3.1.5.3 Advantages over alternatives

Same as technology alternatives defined in section 3.1.3

3.1.6 Technology exploration component Advance Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Unstructured Data

3.1.6.1 Technologies used

The Advanced Data Mining Engine for Unstructured Data will process unstructured data with the aim of uncovering hidden patterns and extracting knowledge, more specifically from text data, as regards the acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies amongst travelers and border guards.

Some of the data sources which are fed in this component are the following:

- Social media data
 - Twitter, reviews, web
- Text from questionnaires
- Text from tablet and mobile METICOS app
- Potentially images

Regarding the processing of the text, state-of-the-art Machine Learning methods will be employed, focusing on the field of Natural Language Processing. Some of these methods and techniques are the following:

- Sentiment analysis (Polarity, Subjectivity)
- Topic modelling
- Context of discussion
- Descriptive analytics
- Keyword extraction
- Named Entity Extraction
- Descriptive analytics

In order to derive the aforementioned outputs, we aim to deploy a standard practice in NLP, a pipeline, using the CRISP-DM Model. The CRISP-DM Model is a Cross-industry standard process for data mining, known as CRISP-DM, which is an open standard process model that describes common approaches used by data mining experts. It is the most widely used analytics model. Typically, any NLP-based problem can be solved by a methodical workflow that has a sequence of steps, which are depicted in Figure 5 [4]:

Figure 5 CRISP-DM Pipeline [4]

The text preprocessing includes the following manipulations in the data: converting text into lower case, removing HTML tags, expanding contractions, converting numbers into words, or removing numbers, removing special character (punctuations, accent marks, and other diacritics), removing white spaces, word tokenization, stemming and lemmatization, removing stop words, sparse terms, and particular words.

Especially for the Twitter data, the following pipeline will be deployed:

Figure 6 Pipeline for Twitter data

Regarding the tools and technologies which have already be used in the development of this component, Python is mainly used, in addition to task-specific (NLP) libraries. Regarding the collection of Twitter data, the Twitter API v2 will be used, since we have obtained an academic account access. Regarding any other textual data collected from the Web, web crawlers are implemented using BeautifulSoup, which is the most popular library for web crawling.

Some of the envisaged libraries for the NLP pipeline include the following [5]:

- **Gensim:** It is a famous python library for natural language processing tasks. It provides a special feature to identify semantic similarity between two documents by the use of vector space modelling and the topic modelling toolkit. It provides a set of algorithms that are very useful in natural language tasks such as Hierarchical Dirichlet Process (HDP), Random Projections (RP), Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA/SVD/LSI) or word2vec deep learning. The most advanced feature of GenSim is its processing speed and fantastic memory usage optimization. [6]
- **Spacy:** It is a proficient, clear open-source python Natural language processing library. It is mainly designed for production usage - to build real-world projects and it helps to handle a large number of text data. This toolkit is written in python in Cython, which makes it efficient to handle a large amount of text data. Some of the features of SpaCy are the fact that it

provides multi trained transformers like BERT, it is extremely fast, and provides multilingual capabilities (55 trained pipelines in more than 17 languages.) [7]

- **PolyGlot:** it offers an expansive scope of analysis and great language inclusion (for instance, for sentiment analysis it supports almost 180 languages). On account of NumPy, it likewise is very fast. [8]
- **CoreNLP:** Stanford CoreNLP contains a grouping of human language innovation instruments, to make the use of semantic analysis tools simple and proficient. The tool consolidates various Stanford's NLP tools, such as sentiment analysis, part-of-speech (POS) tagger, bootstrapped pattern learning, parser, named entity recognizer (NER), coreference resolution system. [9]

Other interesting libraries which are already included in our pipeline are VADER, TextBlob, and in the future we aim to include deep learning libraries such tensorflow, huggingface, transformers, keras etc. for the processing of textual data.

3.1.6.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

The main technological alternatives we have identified with an extensive literature review, which provide the same flexibility and customization are other programming language, such as R, Scala, Java.

3.1.6.3 Advantages over alternatives

Python is used by most practitioners in the field of NLP. It boasts a large, collaborative community and numerous libraries with many tools usable out of the box, and these features make Python excellent for prototyping and experimenting.

Python is well supported with an ever-expanding community and extensive documentation. Moreover, it offers a wide variety of equally community-supported, open-source, robust and flexible libraries to support the development of a robust NLP pipeline. The aforementioned libraries are extremely powerful and proven able to perform a vast variety of tasks in the field of NLP obtaining excellent results. Last but not least, we have acquired experience in Python in various previous projects.

Python was preferred over other open-source data mining programming languages, such as R, for various reasons. Unlike Python, R was not developed as a general-purpose programming language, hence often the programs can be slower. Moreover, R has a steepest learning curve compared to Python in most cases.

Due to the above reasons, the choice of an open-source, mature, widely used technology will provide the most effective way to leverage unstructured data in the METICOS ecosystem. Therefore, the advantage over the alternatives is apparent, as it enables flexibility, extensibility, and support from a large community of users worldwide.

3.1.7 Technology exploration component Advance Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Structured Data

3.1.7.1 Technologies used

The Advanced Data Mining Engine for Structured Data will process structured data with the aim of uncovering hidden patterns and extracting knowledge and correlations between the acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies and influencing factors, amongst travelers and border guards.

Some of the data sources which will be fed in this component are the following:

- Structured data from questionnaires

- Structured data from tablet and mobile METICOS app
- BCP specific Key Performance Indicators
 - E.g. waiting time, queue length, False Acceptance Rate, aggregated demographics as a timeseries etc
- Structured data from responses to TAM questionnaire

For the development of this module Python will be used. Depending on the nature of the data, some of the methods envisaged to be applied are the following: Supervised (Regression, Classification) and Unsupervised (Clustering).

Some of the algorithms we aim to include in the processing of the data are: Neural Networks (LSTM, CNN, ANN), Bayesian Networks, Decision trees (C4.5, ID3), Ensemble methods (Adaboost, Bagging tree, Stacking tree), SVM, Random Forest, Linear Regression, KNN, DBSCAN.

Before applying the aforementioned algorithms, the data need to be prepared accordingly (data processing and cleaning, outliers removal, feature extraction and engineering, feature scaling and selection) and after the application of the respective algorithm, the model needs to be evaluated and tuned before deployment. The different steps of the pipeline are illustrated in Figure 7 :

Figure 7 Machine Learning Pipeline [10]

In order to implement the above pipeline, we envisage to use a selection of the plethora of available open-source Python libraries, some of which are described below [11]:

- **Tensorflow:** Developed by Google Brain Team, TensorFlow is an open-source library used for deep learning applications. Originally developed for numerical compilations, it offers a comprehensive and flexible ecosystem of tools, libraries and community resources, enabling developers to build and deploy ML-based applications. [12]
- **SciKit-Learn:** SciKit-Learn features classification, regression and clustering algorithms, including DBSCAN, gradient boosting, support vector machines and random forests. David Cournapeau built the library on top of SciPy, NumPy and Matplotlib for handling standard machine learning and data mining applications. [13]
- **SciPy:** SciPy provides user-friendly and efficient numerical routines for linear algebra, statistics, integration and optimisation. Its applications include multidimensional image processing, solving Fourier transforms and differential equations. [14]

3.1.7.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

The main technological alternatives to develop a custom robust pipeline for processing of structured data are other programming languages, such as R, Scala, Java.

3.1.7.3 Advantages over alternatives

Python is widely used for data science also in processing structured data and applying to them Machine Learning and Deep Learning algorithms. It boasts a large, collaborative community and numerous libraries with many tools usable out of the box, and these features make Python excellent for prototyping and experimenting.

Python is well supported with a strong community of users and developers and extensive documentation. Moreover, it offers a wide variety of equally community-supported, open-source, robust and flexible libraries to support the development of a Machine Learning pipeline. The aforementioned libraries are extremely powerful and proven able to perform a vast variety of tasks obtaining excellent results. Last but not least, we have acquired experience in Python in various previous projects. Moreover, Python was preferred over other open-source data mining programming languages, such as R for instance, since R is claimed to have a steepest learning curve compared to Python in most cases.

Due to the above reasons, the choice of Python as an open-source, mature, widely used technology will provide the most effective way to leverage knowledge from structured data in METICOS. Therefore, the advantage over the alternatives is apparent, as it enables flexibility, extensibility, and support from a large community of users worldwide.

3.1.8 Technology exploration component Cross-sectorial (big) data analysis mechanisms

3.1.8.1 Technologies used

The Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Mechanisms module aims to analyse and aggregate data from different sources, locations and formats. This will be achieved by being the centralising point of the output of other components (ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data). The data coming from various components will be fused and processed accordingly in order to deduce knowledge not from individual datasets but from their fusion. Data fusion implies often the concatenation of data sets that present an enormous diversity in terms of information, size, and behavior. The pieces of information connected reflect the variation apportioned by components, events, or sources that are differently represented and, yet, complement each other in the data blocks analyzed simultaneously. [15]

Building upon the results of each dataset (incl. data sources providing structured & unstructured data, output from other METICOS components), this module will calculate the overall acceptance score for all BCPs and the correlations/dependencies of different criteria with the acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies. Moreover, this module will transfer the knowledge acquired from one defined so-called “sector” to another, and be able to provide useful knowledge, and potentially predictions, to sectors where some data assets are missing.

Some ML algorithms which would be well-suited for this component come from Deep Learning, such as Convolutional Neural Networks, Stacked Autoencoders (SAEs) and Generative Adversarial Networks. (GANs). At the moment we are examining various Big Data Analytics tools so that offer efficient, robust and flexible capabilities. Currently, we are leaning toward using Python for the implementation of this module. Various libraries are taken into account, depending on the nature of the data, their format and their volume, such as SciPy, Scikit-Learn, Keras, TensorFlow etc.

3.1.8.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

The main technological alternatives to develop a custom robust pipeline for the fusion of the acquired datasets and the transfer learning among sectors are other programming languages, such as R, Scala, Java.

3.1.8.3 Advantages over alternatives

Python is widely used for data science also in processing structured data and applying to them Machine Learning and Deep Learning algorithms. It boasts a large, collaborative community and numerous libraries with many tools usable out of the box, and these features make Python excellent for prototyping and experimenting.

Python is well supported with a strong community of users and developers and extensive documentation. Moreover, it offers a wide variety of equally community-supported, open-source, robust and flexible libraries to support the development of a Machine Learning pipeline. The aforementioned libraries are extremely powerful and proven able to perform a vast variety of tasks obtaining excellent results. Last but not least, we have acquired experience in Python in various previous projects. Moreover, Python was preferred over other open-source data mining programming languages, such as R for instance, since R is claimed to have a steepest learning curve compared to Python in most cases.

Due to the above reasons, the choice of Python as an open-source, mature, widely used technology will provide the most effective way to leverage knowledge from structured data in METICOS. Therefore, the advantage over the alternatives is apparent, as it enables flexibility, extensibility, and support from a large community of users worldwide.

3.1.9 Technology exploration component Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit

3.1.9.1 Technologies used

The DTVA module will provide a data dashboard to the METICOS key stakeholders, namely policy makers and border authorities. It will be an information management tool that visually tracks, analyzes and displays key performance indicator (KPI) metrics and key data points to monitor the acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.

Some of the outputs that DTVA will expose to the end-users are:

- Results from analysis from other WP7 components (see 3.1.6, 3.1.7, 3.1.8)
- Results from the output of ETAP module
- Raw data in specific cases (e.g. display of twitter stream for individual BCPs etc.)

There are various commercial and open-source tools in order to build a robust, flexible, interactive dashboard module. At the moment, we are focusing our attention to Grafana.

A Grafana dashboard is a powerful open source analytical and visualization tool that consists of multiple individual panels arranged in a grid. It offers the possibility to visualize results from multiple data sources simultaneously. The purpose of Grafana dashboards is to bring data together in a way that is both efficient and organized. It allows users to better understand the metrics of their data through queries, informative visualizations, and alerts. [16]

Another key aspect of Grafana dashboards is the fact that they are open source, which allows for even more customization and power, depending on how comfortable you are with coding. However, you do not need extensive knowledge of coding to create a fully functioning Grafana dashboard. [16]

Moreover, some python libraries are envisaged to be used in order to visualize the results of the Big Data Analysis, such as Seaborn, Plotly, Matplotlib, Geoplotlib, Bokeh etc. The outputs of this visualization will be included in the dashboard.

3.1.9.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

The main technological alternatives are:

- Commercial tools
 - o Tableau
 - o Power BI
 - o Dash enterprise
 - o Freeboard
- Custom Web development using
 - o Python (flask)
 - o React framework
 - o Angular framework
 - o JavaScript

3.1.9.3 Advantages over alternatives

Grafana is the perfect tool for visualizing time series data. But that's not all - the creators and maintainers of Grafana define it as an overall "open observatory platform". The dashboard contains a grid of panels with different visualizations in them. You can organize dashboards into folders and assign different permissions to them.

The concept of Grafana is very broad, while Tableau for instance, is more focused on business intelligence. On the other hand, custom web development is also possible, but it will require much more effort and time, whereas the open-source Grafana offers great functionality and a professional look-and-feel almost out-of-the-box. In addition, it has a variety of plugins and it enables customization.

Grafana is an excellent tool to serve complex needs and various sources of data, it provides a powerful query builder and interactive timeseries and other plots. It is clear, professional and offers flexibility of customization. That is why the choice of such a mature and proven technology will provide the most effective way for METICOS to provide the end users with a powerful interactive dashboard exposing the insights of the Big Data Analytics components and other METICOS modules.

3.1.10 Technology exploration component Interfaces with Border and Customs Management Information Systems

The scope of the project was changed so the METICOS system will not connect to custom identification systems or BCP risk assessment platforms. Further to this METICOS platform will not be connected with any VIS or ISIS or any other border information system for security reasons. This component will be modified or will be no longer implemented in v2.

3.1.11 Technology exploration component Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform

The scope of the project was changed, as there is not any available risk assessment platform in METICOS BCPs, so the METICOS system will not connect to custom identification systems or BCP risk assessment platforms. Further to this METICOS platform will not be connected with any VIS or ISIS or any other border information system for security reasons. This component will be modified or will be no longer implemented in v2.

3.1.12 Technology exploration component Data integration module (CDME)

3.1.12.1 Technologies used

In the development of the CDME component we will use the following FIWARE components: Orion Context Broker, Cygnus, Keyrock, Wilma. FIWARE is a framework of open source components created to accelerate the development of Smart Solutions with. These components are the implementations of open standards created also under the FIWARE umbrella. The FIWARE initiative was partially funded by the European Commission. [17] [18]

- Orion Context Broker is an implementation of FIWARE NGSI v2 API that enables updates, queries or subscriptions to changes of context information [19]
- Cygnus is a component that accompanies Orion Context Broker and allows the management of the history of the context as a stream of data that can be sent to multiple data sinks (for example databases like PostgreSQL, MySQL, MongoDB or big data platform like Hadoop, Storm, Flink) [19]
- Keyrock is an identity management component supporting OAuth2-based authentication of users and devices, user profile management, privacy-preserving disposition of personal data, single sign-on [19]
- Wilma is a component that brings support to proxy functions within OAuth2-based authentication schemas and implements PEP (Policy Enforcement Point) functions within an XACML-based access control schema [19]

In order to share data with other systems, we will use HDF (Hierarchical Data Format). HDF is a data file format specialized in the storage and manipulation of scientific data. An HDF file can store description of the data, making it self-describing, it can store heterogeneous data (data sets, images). The HDF format is a portable, platform independent format. [20]

3.1.12.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

The alternatives to FIWARE components presented above are represented by messaging systems combined with relational database systems.

Possible messaging systems:

- Kafka
- ApacheMQ
- RabbitMQ

Database systems:

- PostgreSQL
- MySQL/MariaDB
- MS SQL Server
- Oracle DB

Alternatives to HDF consist in nosql database systems:

- MongoDB
- CouchDB
- OrientDB

Also, text files or other binary formats could be considered alternatives to HDF.

3.1.12.3 Advantages over alternatives

All the alternatives presented are good products that could be used in this project.

We have chosen FIWARE components considering that they are based on open standards, the FIWARE ecosystem is a rich ecosystem. Orion Broker maintains a context information that is updated continuously, is able to model heterogeneous information and can be used in any domain because it is domain-independent. These are important considerations for METICOS system, because it will handle heterogeneous data coming from border control points. [21]

HDF was chosen because it is very used for storing and sharing information in research area. It also has some characteristics important for this project [22]:

- It supports heterogeneous data
- It is portable and self describing
- It supports high-performance I/O
- It allows to keep metadata with data

There is an important number of APIs in different programming languages that support HDF (C, C++, Python, Java etc.). It is also supported by a large number of libraries, including numpy that is used by other METICOS components.

3.1.13 Technology exploration component Middleware

3.1.13.1 Technologies used

Java Spring Boot (Spring Boot) is a tool that makes developing web application and microservices with Spring Framework faster and easier through three core capabilities:

1. Autoconfiguration
2. An opinionated approach to configuration
3. The ability to create standalone applications

These features work together to provide you with a tool that allows you to set up a Spring-based application with minimal configuration and setup.

Spring Boot is basically an extension of the Spring framework, which eliminates the boilerplate configurations required for setting up a Spring application. It takes an opinionated view of the Spring platform, which paves the way for a faster and more efficient development ecosystem.

Spring boot features

- Opinionated 'starter' dependencies to simplify the build and application configuration
- Embedded server to avoid complexity in application deployment
- Metrics, Health check, and externalized configuration
- Automatic config for Spring functionality – whenever possible
- Create stand-alone Spring applications
- Provide production-ready features such as metrics, health checks, and externalized configuration
- Absolutely no code generation and no requirement for XML configuration

3.1.13.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

.NET Core: .NET is a free, cross-platform, open-source developer platform for building many different types of applications. With .NET, you can use multiple languages, editors, and libraries to build for web, mobile, desktop, games, and IoT.

Laravel is an open-source PHP framework. It follows a model-view-controller design pattern. Laravel reuses the existing components of different frameworks which helps in creating a web application. Laravel offers a rich set of functionalities which incorporates the basic features of PHP frameworks like CodeIgniter, Yii and other programming languages like Ruby on Rails. Laravel has a very rich set of features which will boost the speed of web development.

3.1.13.3 Advantages over alternatives

Spring boot has the following benefits:

- It provides powerful batch processing and manages REST endpoints.
- In Spring Boot, everything is auto configured; no manual configurations are needed.
- It offers annotation-based spring application.
- Eases dependency management.
- It includes Embedded Servlet Container.
- Spring Boot allows you to create applications without requiring any XML configuration.
- Spring Boot provides a fluent builder API through the Spring Application Builder singleton class that allows you to create hierarchies with multiple application contexts.
- Spring is an Opinionated technology which means the spring boot will attempt to create the right type of application, either a web application (embedding Tomcat or Jetty Container) or a single application.
- Spring Boot allows you to configure and use logging very simply.
- Spring Boot provides a simple way to configure and manage your dependencies by using starter poms.
- Spring Boot provides out-of-the-box on-functional requirements by using the Spring Boot Actuator, so you can see the health memory and so on, of your application.

3.1.14 Technology exploration component Front End

3.1.14.1 Technologies used

The METICOS Front-End component will be implemented in Vue JavaScript. Vue.js is an open-source progressive JavaScript framework for building user interfaces (UIs) and single-page applications. Unlike other monolithic frameworks, Vue is designed from the ground up to be incrementally adoptable. The core library is focused on the view layer only, and is easy to pick up and integrate with other libraries or existing projects.

The framework uses “high decoupling”, allowing developers to progressively create user interfaces (UIs). Library modularization using a framework is common in frontend development. Both React and Angular have modularization. The fact that differentiates Vue.js from other alternatives is its ability in “high decoupling”, how easy it is to extend functionalities, and how well all parts work once more modules are included. For small visual components we use Vue.js’s ‘core’ library. As the application grows, existing libraries are used to manage; routes such as ‘vue-router’, the global state such as ‘vuex’ or libraries to build responsive web applications such as ‘bootstrap-vue’. Additionally, if the application needs to be optimized, the ‘vue-server-rendering’ library can be included.

Vue.js’s component system is reactive, meaning that Vue.js knows how to communicate through asynchronous events; a child component can communicate with its parent component through events. With Vue.js there is no friction with other libraries or resources, in other words, we can use the tool with which we are most comfortable with. For example, we can write only HTML and JavaScript or if we want, we can add CSS, JSX or TypeScript.

Vue.js has a special command line (CLI) created on Node JS. This tool allows to start a project using a boilerplate (or base template). Additionally, the Vue.js development team maintains a Chrome extension that allows us to see how our component tree is rendered, how events are being launched and recorded, how the internal state of each component is saved, and how the global state of the component is behaving.

3.1.14.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

React (also known as React.js or ReactJS) is a free and open-source front-end JavaScript library for building user interfaces or UI components. It is responsible only for the application's view layer. React can be used as a base in the development of single-page or mobile applications. However, React is only concerned with state management and rendering that state to the DOM, so creating React applications usually requires the use of additional libraries for routing, as well as certain client-side functionality.

Angular is a platform and framework for building single-page client applications using HTML and TypeScript. Angular is written in TypeScript. It implements core and optional functionality as a set of TypeScript libraries that you import into your applications. The architecture of an Angular application relies on certain fundamental concepts. The basic building blocks of the Angular framework are Angular components that are organized into NgModules.

3.1.14.3 Advantages over alternatives

What differentiates this framework from other JavaScript web development frameworks is that

- **It is open-source:** Angular is backed by Google, React is backed by Facebook, but Vue.js is entirely backed by the open-source community.
- **Easy to learn:** the only prerequisite for understanding it is to understand the 'big three' web development technologies: JavaScript, HTML, and CSS.
- **Adaptable:** its architecture is designed to be incrementally adaptable.
- **Lightweight framework:** the framework it is lightweight for this reason building apps is quicker.
- **Combines Angular's and React's best features:** it is inspired by Angular and React, it learns from and takes all the best features of both Angular and React, while discarding the not-so-good ones.
- **Model-View-ViewModel (MVVM) Architecture:** The MVVM architecture that Vue.js uses is excellent for enhancing UI experience. MVVM simplifies user interface event-driven programming. This improves system performance

3.1.15 Technology exploration component Border Checkpoint and Mobile App for passengers

3.1.15.1 Technologies used

Vue Native is a JavaScript framework designed to build cross-platform mobile applications that can run on both Android and iOS with JavaScript. It is designed to connect React Native and Vue.js. By wrapping around React Native, developers can use Vue Native to build mobile applications using Vue.js.

Because of this, everything that can be done in React Native can be done in Vue Native, and code is compiled down to React Native. This way, developers benefit from what the Vue and React Native ecosystems offer.

The Vue ecosystem is one of the largest and fastest-growing ecosystems in the JavaScript space. Building an app with Vue Native provides the benefits of the larger Vue ecosystem.

Key features of Vue Native:

- Declarative rendering
- Two-way binding
- Goodness of Vue ecosystem
- Compiles to React Native
- Completeness of React Native ecosystem

3.1.15.2 Brief description of the main technological alternatives

React Native is an UI software framework created by Facebook, Inc. It is used to develop applications for Android, Android TV, iOS, macOS, tvOS, Web, Windows and UWP by enabling developers to use the React framework along with native platform capabilities.

The working principles of React Native are virtually identical to React, except that React Native does not manipulate the DOM via the Virtual DOM. It runs in a background process (which interprets the JavaScript written by the developers) directly on the end-device and communicates with the native platform via serialized data over an asynchronous and batched bridge. React components wrap existing native code and interact with native APIs via React's declarative UI paradigm and JavaScript.

While React Native styling has a similar syntax to CSS, it does not use HTML or CSS. Instead, messages from the JavaScript thread are used to manipulate native views. React Native also allows developers to write native code in languages such as Java or Kotlin for Android, Objective-C or Swift for iOS, and C++/WinRT or C# for Windows 10, which makes it even more flexible.

3.1.15.3 Advantages over alternatives

- Because Vue Native uses React Native packages to access mobile device APIs, developers can access React Native's community and its libraries.
- Vue apps are generally slightly faster than React apps.
- Vue's framework has the easiest learning curve. Vue's syntax is easier to read and more concise than React Native's syntax.
- Vue Native is under the MIT license, you don't have any copyright concerns.

4 METICOS System Architecture

The METICOS project is based on two paradigm-changing, timely and essential issues: 1) the need for efficient, simpler but safer Smart Borders and 2) the requirement to measure the travellers' satisfaction and societal and political acceptance on the usage of Smart Borders technologies.

METICOS will implement a technological platform and define metrics for evaluation of: 1) the effectiveness and efficiency of Smart Borders technologies and 2) the travellers' satisfaction and acceptability on the employment of those technologies and 3) the level of future proofing is enhanced with the flexibility to add new data sources as threats evolve. METICOS platform are going to be a valuable tool for border management for more efficient, fast and effective next generation Smart Borders.

METICOS system is based on a Service Oriented Architecture, using privacy by design principles that must enable secure exchange, processing, and storage of border related data. Data is collected, exchanged and processed at multiple architectural levels, and over communication protocols with differing security guarantees.

4.1 Stakeholders and concerns

The stakeholders were identified and described in detail in the deliverable D4.1 "User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis". The main categories of stakeholders are:

- BCP staff (border guards, immigration officers, customs officers, police authorities)
- Policy/Decision makers (National Policy Makers, data privacy expert, Ethics and human rights expert)
- Travelers
- Developers

Each category of stakeholder is interested in certain characteristics of the system, representing their concerns about the system. Here's a mapping between the categories of stakeholders and typical and relevant concerns about the type of system this project is aiming to create.

Stakeholders / Concerns	Functionality	Security	Privacy	Usability	Modularity	Compliance to regulation	Business goals
BCP staff	x	x	x	x		x	x
Policy/Decision makers		x	x			x	x
Travelers		x	x	x			
Developers	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

The summary about these concerns:

- *Functionality* is about the system delivering the expected results as presented in the user requirements;
- *Security, Privacy, Compliance to regulation* are important topics especially considering the nature of this project and the type of data used by it;
- *Usability* means that the system should be easy to use; it should have a minimum overhead, especially for travelers;
- *Modularity* implies also concerns like maintainability, flexibility and scalability. This concerns mainly the developers of the system;
- *Business goals* is about the system giving to the policy/decision makers the information needed to create and implement new policies that improve the smart border concept.

The architecture was developed considering these concerns in order for the system to bring value to stakeholders.

4.2 Logical Architecture

The proposed architecture (Figure 8 METICOS Logical Architecture) consists of several METICOS Producer and METICOS Consumer services. The services will be packaged into containers along with all the software necessary to support self-contained deployment of the service (runtime environment, libraries for supported communication protocols, encryption techniques, etc.).

Figure 8 METICOS Logical Architecture

The proposed concept is broken down to the following components:

1. The **Front-end** Graphical User Interface of the whole system, including intuitive and highly comprehensive visual analytics to enable human-information discourse, a user-friendly design based on human cognitive and perceptual principles as well as efficient interaction methodologies.
2. A multi-parametric **Technology Acceptance Predictor** for the various data sources (e.g. data made available by BCP, travelers feedback etc.)
3. **Data collectors** with crawling, pre-process and data storing capabilities for multimodal data in real time, as they are provided by the authorized inter-disciplinary sources (i.e. data made available by BCP, social media with focus in Twitter, RSS feeds & pdf reports). These components will also be responsible for the seamless fusion of the data into less noisy (e.g. de-noising, dimensionality reduction techniques, etc.) & more informative outcomes.
4. **Data analyzer** that detects correlations and patterns in large amounts of data and will lead to the extraction of information rich feature & metadata.

6. **METICOS data repository for secured storage / sharing of data** between the partners of all the openly collected unstructured data (incl. processed information & metadata), as well as some of their proprietary data according to the use case.

To automate the data collection process and make it more efficient, METICOS will elaborate on the design and implementation of a secure IT infrastructure (METICOS middleware, Private Cloud Backend), software tools and connectors that border staff will utilize for on-line and real time traveller’s data exchange with the METICOS engine, alongside the technical requirements and specifications for the underlying networking infrastructure capable of interconnecting with BCPs, not only within the same country (intra-country communication), but also and most importantly the BCPs located in different states (inter-country communication). Such intra/inter BCP/METICOS communication will be conducted through a distributed (e.g. instances located in different European states) METICOS Orchestrator entity, and will be carried over Secured Network and Interfaces.

4.3 Process View

The process view captures the dynamic nature of the system. It describes the interactions between the system components. Here we present a sequence diagram showing how components work together. The upper part of the diagram describes an ongoing process of collecting and persisting the data in the data repository. The lower part of the diagram describes the interaction with the BCP staff, how the system’s users have access to the results produced by the platform.

Figure 9 Sequence diagram of METICOS

4.4 Development View

The development view presents details about the software components organisation. It describes the relationships and the collaboration between components it also presents technological decisions. In the diagram shown below, the SoA technical decisions are highlighted: components are packaged in containers and decisions about the development approaches (Spring, Vuejs, Python) and supporting software (nginx webserver) are set.

Figure 10 METICOS Application Architecture

4.4.1 Components

The METICOS platform will consist of several components with well-defined functionalities and responsibilities. Each component implements a specific business service, like technology acceptance, data mining, simulation and it will be developed by a different partner. To integrate them and function like a whole, the communication and data exchange between components is realized with a well-defined contract (API or database schema).

The core architectural components of the METICOS platform are outlined below:

The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travelers, border authorities). The ETAP module is based on one or more probabilistic technology acceptance models (TAMs) which are developed during the project. Each TAM consists of several components that reflect the most relevant key aspects (perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, etc.) of acceptance of smart border control technologies. This component is detailed in chapter 3.2 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.2](#) from this document.

The Socio-Cultural Framework Module (SCFM) will allow the METICOS platform to assess the main reasons behind possible misunderstandings that may occur when individuals with different socio-cultural backgrounds will try to pass through new BCP technologies. This module will provide inputs to the **METICOS Social Toolkit**. This component is detailed in chapter 3.3 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.4](#) from this document.

The Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) will define a specific threshold for each BCP technology when dealing with non-EU travellers. It will be an external component supporting the METICOS Social Toolkit with continuous feeds from real-time data. The module will use information collected from different sources, mostly related to the different technologies and devices in use, such as the overall complexity of the device/technology used, the level of interaction with different users, response time, the level of flexibility, level of necessary support from border authorities etc. This component is detailed in chapter 3.4 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.5](#) from this document.

The Social Toolkit Module will contribute into achieving the objective of continuously monitoring the social acceptance considering the different behavioral patterns of the people and the interactions between them trying to pass the EU border control systems. Since the final objective would be to evolve towards *a safe and effective no gate solution*, this module should progress towards achieving this final state and provide related outcomes. This component is detailed in chapter 3.5 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.3](#) from this document.

The Interface with Border and Customs Management Information Systems will ingest the data that border authorities will make available for the METICOS platform. METICOS project will not connect to custom identification systems or BCP risk assessment platforms. *The Interface with Border and Customs Management Information Systems* is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing data without security or privacy issues that BPC make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservices that offer information like queue lengths, average waiting times, late flights or a custom component that connects to the METICOS systems and sends the data agreed with the BPC.

The Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module will process and analyze structured data from various sources in order to uncover the correlations amongst variables of the

raw data, regarding the technology acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies. This component is detailed in chapter 3.7 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.7](#) from this document.

The Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module will gather and analyze unstructured data from different sources. The end goal of the module is to uncover the hidden patterns amongst variables of the raw data, concerning the technology and societal acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies. This component is detailed in chapter 3.8 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.6](#) from this document.

The Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Module will infer the acceptance of a BCP or technology by aggregating and analyzing data from different sources, locations and formats. It accepts as input the aforementioned data as well as the outputs of other components (ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data, and others). The output of the CS-BDA component will be fed in the DTVA component. This component is detailed in chapter 3.9 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.8](#) from this document.

The Interactive Visual Analytics Technologies component will provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyze correlations of data generated from other METICOS components (for instance the Social Toolkit module and the Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction module) as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies. This component is detailed in chapter 3.10 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.9](#) from this document.

The METICOS Middleware Module aims at creating adaptors for accumulating and aggregating information from a number of mobile terminals and cameras (hard real-time data). To this end, it uses Web Services, a standardized medium to propagate communication between the client and server applications, by providing a common platform that allows multiple applications built on various programming languages to have the ability to communicate with each other. This component is detailed in chapter 3.11 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.13](#) from this document.

The Smart Front-End Infrastructure Module provides an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. This component is detailed in chapter 3.12 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.14](#) from this document.

The Common Data Management Engine (CDME) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way. All the exchanged information will be translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all METICOS components use them. This component is detailed in chapter 3.14 from deliverable “D4.1 User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis” and in chapter [3.1.12](#) from this document.

4.5 Deployment Architecture

For the first iteration of the METICOS platform, it will be deployed on a central server in SIMAVI’s data center.

At each BPC, there will be an instance of the component “Interfaces with Border and Customs Middleware” (in case it is implemented as custom component that connects to the METICOS systems

and sends the data agreed with the BPC, as explained in the previous section) and tablets for collecting traveller feedback.

Figure 11 Sequence diagram of METICOS

The server used for platform deployment has the following characteristics:

Server characteristic	Value
OS	Ubuntu 20.04.3
CPU Core count	16
RAM	64 GB
HDD storage	500 GB

As infrastructure software, the server contains Docker and Kubernetes. There is also a docker registry instance that will be used to manage the docker images of METICOS components. They are described in the following sections.

4.5.1 Docker

Docker is a software platform that allows building, testing, and deploying applications quickly. Docker packages software into standardized units called containers that have everything the software needs to run including libraries, system tools, code, and runtime. Using Docker, applications can be quickly deployed and scaled into any environment.

Docker is a set of the platform as a service (PaaS) products that use OS-level virtualization to deliver software in packages called containers. Containers are isolated from one another and bundle their own software, libraries, and configuration files; they can communicate with each other through well-defined channels. Because all of the containers share the services of a single operating system kernel, they use fewer resources than virtual machines. [23]

Designing the deployment architecture involves sizing the deployment to determine the physical resources necessary to meet the system requirements specified during the technical requirements phase. METICOS will use virtualization technologies as Docker and Kubernetes, which are now the most useful and efficient technologies.

All components from the project will use Docker containers and will be orchestrated with Kubernetes.

Container technology can be thought of as three different categories:

1. **Builder**: a tool or series of tools used to build a container, such as distrobuilder for LXC, or a Dockerfile for Docker.

2. Engine: an application used to run a container. For Docker, this refers to the docker command and the dockerd daemon. For others, this can refer to the containerd daemon and relevant commands.
3. Orchestration: technology used to manage many containers, including Kubernetes.

Docker is used to create a Docker image of the application by using a Docker file. A Docker file has all the instructions on how to build the final image for deployment and distribution. The images that are made are reusable perpetually. The image is then used by Kubernetes for the deployment. The benefits of Docker are, for example, the reusability of once-created resources and the fast setup of the target environment, whether it is for testing or production purposes. This is achieved through container technologies made possible by Docker and Kubernetes.

Once the Docker image is created with the Docker platform, it is ready to be used with the Kubernetes container platform. With the Docker platform a base image is created, which is then used by the Kubernetes deployment platform. The ease-of-deployment eliminates possible human errors in the process, which makes the deployment reliable, efficient and quick. The reason Kubernetes was selected is its versatility, scalability and the potential automatization of the deployment process. The technologies are not new and are being developed every day to improve the end-user experience.

With Docker and Kubernetes, it is possible to create a continuous integration-and deployment-pipeline which, for example, guarantees a quickly deployed development version of an application to be tested locally.

4.5.2 Docker Registry

The Docker Registry is a stateless, highly scalable server-side application that stores and lets you distribute Docker images. The Registry is open-source, under the permissive Apache license.

Docker Registry is used to:

- Tightly control where your storing of Docker images
- fully own your Docker images distribution pipeline
- integrate image storage and distribution tightly into the in-house development workflow

A Docker registry is a storage and distribution system for named Docker images. The same image might have multiple different versions, identified by their tags.

A Docker registry is organized into Docker repositories, where a repository holds all the versions of a specific image. The registry allows Docker users to pull images locally, as well as push new images to the registry (given adequate access permissions when applicable).

By default, the Docker engine interacts with DockerHub , Docker’s public registry instance. However, it is possible to run on-premises the open-source Docker registry/distribution.

Public registry services are basic, simple to use and can work well for individuals and smaller teams. But once teams begin to scale up, they run into numerous issues with public registries. A private container registry with scanning capabilities and role-based access control offers more security, governance and efficient management.

Figure 12 Private Docker Registry

Use cases for running a private registry on-premises (internal to the organization) include:

- Distributing images inside an isolated network (not sending images over the Internet)
- Creating faster CI/CD pipelines (pulling and pushing images from internal network), including faster deployments to on-premises environments
- Deploying a new image over a large cluster of machines

Running a private registry system, especially when delivery to production depends on it, requires operational skills such as ensuring availability, logging and log processing, monitoring, and security. Strong understanding of http and overall network communications is also important.

4.5.3 Kubernetes

Kubernetes is an open-source container-orchestration system for automating computer application deployment, scaling, and management. It was originally designed by Google and is now maintained by the Cloud Native Computing Foundation. It aims to provide a "platform for automating deployment, scaling, and operations of application containers across clusters of hosts". It works with a range of container tools and runs containers in a cluster, often with images built using Docker. Kubernetes originally interfaced with the Docker.. [24]

Figure 13 Evolution of deployment

Traditional deployment era: Early on, organizations ran applications on physical servers. There was no way to define resource boundaries for applications in a physical server, and this caused resource allocation issues. For example, if multiple applications run on a physical server, there can be instances where one application would take up most of the resources, and as a result, the other applications would underperform. A solution for this would be to run each application on a different physical server. But this did not scale as resources were underutilized, and it was expensive for organizations to maintain many physical servers.

Virtualized deployment era: As a solution, virtualization was introduced. It allows you to run multiple Virtual Machines (VMs) on a single physical server's CPU. Virtualization allows applications to be isolated between VMs and provides a level of security as the information of one application cannot be freely accessed by another application.

Virtualization allows better utilization of resources in a physical server and allows better scalability because an application can be added or updated easily, reduces hardware costs, and much more. With virtualization you can present a set of physical resources as a cluster of disposable virtual machines. Each VM is a full machine running all the components, including its own operating system, on top of the virtualized hardware.

Container deployment era: Containers are similar to VMs, but they have relaxed isolation properties to share the Operating System (OS) among the applications. Therefore, containers are considered lightweight. Like a VM, a container has its own filesystem, share of CPU, memory, process space, and more. As they are decoupled from the underlying infrastructure, they are portable across clouds and OS distributions.

Containers have become popular because they provide extra benefits, such as:

- Agile application creation and deployment: increased ease and efficiency of container image creation compared to VM image use.
- Continuous development, integration, and deployment: provides for reliable and frequent container image build and deployment with quick and efficient rollbacks (due to image immutability).
- Dev and Ops separation of concerns: create application container images at build/release time rather than deployment time, thereby decoupling applications from infrastructure.
- Observability: not only surfaces OS-level information and metrics, but also application health and other signals.
- Environmental consistency across development, testing, and production: Runs the same on a laptop as it does in the cloud.
- Cloud and OS distribution portability: Runs on Ubuntu, RHEL, CoreOS, on-premises, on major public clouds, and anywhere else.
- Application-centric management: Raises the level of abstraction from running an OS on virtual hardware to running an application on an OS using logical resources.
- Loosely coupled, distributed, elastic, liberated micro-services: applications are broken into smaller, independent pieces and can be deployed and managed dynamically – not a monolithic stack running on one big single-purpose machine.
- Resource isolation: predictable application performance.

- Resource utilization: high efficiency and density

4.6 Scenarios

As a way to validate the architecture we will consider the following basic scenario:

- Data ingestion - The “Interface with Border and Customs Management Information Systems” component will collect the data that BCPs make available and the data from travellers (via mobile app, questionnaires)
- Data anonymisation – the data is anonymised by the Middleware component
- Data storage – the data is persisted in the Persistence Layer. The sensitive data is encrypted. The data is available for other components for processing.
- Data processing & analysing – this is done by the multiple components
 - Big data analytics engine – process and analyse the heterogeneous data in the persistence layer. Produce new data that is stored in persistence layer.
 - ETAP – process and analyse data and output TAM score
- Visualise – Front end component is used by stakeholders to visualise the TAM score, patterns in the data and insight obtained after analysing the data

5 Conclusions

This deliverable presented the first version of the METICOS platform architecture. The work on the architecture will continue and will be presented in the deliverable D4.7. The METICOS components will be installed on the METICOS server, and the architecture will be validated using the presented scenario in section 4.6 and other scenarios identified in the future. The architecture will be updated based on the findings in the validation process. There will be work on documenting the data flows between components, the interfaces between components and the dependencies between components.

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